

CREEP BEHAVIOR OF GLASS-EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER HYGROTHERMAL CONDITIONS

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Abstract

This paper is concerned with the hygrothermal effects on tensile creep behavior of a glass-fiber reinforced epoxy composite material. In order to describe the creep characteristics of the composite and composite laminates, a typical glass-epoxy system was selected and examined experimentally by means of tensile static and creep tests which were conducted in controlled humidity-temperature environments.

The test specimens were made from Scotchply 1002, a product of the 3-M Company. Unidirectional (both 0° and 90°), $(\pm 45)_S$ crossply, and quasi-isotropic $([90/0/\pm 45]_S)$ laminates were fabricated according to the Vender's recommended procedures. Static tests were performed first in order to establish the baseline data for the various laminates. They were then followed by tensile creep tests at various load-levels with controlled temperature and moisture conditions.

The test temperatures ranged from 75°F (room temperature) to 215°F and the moisture contents in the various test specimens ranged from 0% (dry) to 1.0% (the saturated moisture content for the specimens is approximately 1.5%).

Based on the test results on (0°) , (90°) and $(\pm 45)_S$ laminates, which are termed here as "basic laminates", a simple approximate method was developed to calculate the creep response of any laminates which contain the "basic laminates" in their lamination structure. The method is essentially a macromechanics approach which models the behavior of a laminate upon the knowledge of how the individual elemental components, i.e., the "basic laminates" in the lamination structure, would behave. It is shown that the calculated results correlated quite well with the experimental measurement.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that some solid matters creep under applied loads. It is essentially a time-dependent phenomenon in the form of continuous increase in deformation as time progresses. This time-dependent behavior of the material could play a significant role in the dimensional stability of precision-sensitive structures. Creep behavior of conventional metallic materials has been investigated extensively in the past. For a large number of metallic materials, their tensile creep curves are rather common (1). In general, three periods of time are observed in a typical tensile creep curve. In the first time period, the creep rate is uniformly decreasing; in the second time period, the creep rate remains essentially constant; and in the final period, the creep rate is increasing resulting in the final rupture of the material under stress. These three periods are often called the period of primary creep, secondary creep, and tertiary creep, respectively.

For modern fiber-reinforced composites, the creep response is a rather complicated phenomenon because the material heterogeneity and anisotropy are orders of magnitude different from the common metals. Therefore, the creep strain rate of a composite material may not follow the common trend found in most metals. Particularly for polymer-based composites, such as the glass-epoxy system, there exist other parameters (that influence profoundly the material property), non-linear material behavior, temperature-dependent properties, humidity (or moisture absorption) dependent properties, etc., just to mention a few.

For polymer-based composites, the externally applied stress is also a basic factor in the creep strain rate. This effect varies according to the fiber orientation. For (0°) and to some extent the ($0^\circ/90^\circ$), cross-ply laminates under uniaxial loads, the increase in the instantaneous strain is usually a linear function of the load, while the creep responses during the first and secondary stages of creep follow the general behavior of metals.

For fiber orientation other than 0° , the effect of the matrix properties becomes predominant. Consequently, a non-linear response is usually observed both in the initial strain and the rate of creep. This effect is more evident in the ($\pm 45^\circ$)_S laminates, since the shear property of the matrix is intrinsically non-linear even under small stress.

It has been found that a rise of temperature increases the creep deformation of fiber reinforced polymeric composites (2). This effect may be compounded by the effect of the applied stress resulting in a more severe nonlinearity in the material response. Soliman (3) reported some test results of uniaxial tensile creep and creep rupture of a graphite-epoxy composite tested under different temperatures and different stress levels. From these experiments, it is observed that the creep strain rate increases significantly at elevated temperature, especially under high stress levels. In addition, thermal exposure is also observed to decrease the creep rupture time, especially for the ($\pm 45^\circ$) glass-epoxy specimens (4).

A number of analytical efforts have been made to describe the tensile creep response of polymer-based composites. Recently, McQuillen (5) adopted a micro-mechanics concept (6), based on linear viscoelasticity, and analyzed the creep response for a boron-epoxy system. Wang, McQuillen and Ahmadi (7) extended this theory to include the temperature effect by means of a time-temperature shift technique. Measurements on a type of graphite-epoxy system under a range of stress and temperature levels indicated that the linear viscoelastic model correlate well with experiments only at low temperature and low stress levels. The creep behavior becomes increasingly non-linear with increased stress and/or temperature. Thus, a linear viscoelastic creep model is inadequate under such circumstances.

Moisture effects on the creep response of polymer-based composites have also been noted in recent years. (8). For example, Wang and Liu (9) investigated the creep response of a graphite-epoxy unidirectional laminated composite, with the load

applied only transverse to the fibers. In their study, the combined effects of temperature and humidity were examined. Generally speaking, an increase in humidity and/or temperature will cause an increase of the creep strain rate; the severity of non-linearity increases with increased temperature and/or humidity.

The objective of this paper is to advance observing temperature and moisture effects on the creep responses of composite laminates and to develop a relatively simple method for the calculation of the creep responses of an anisotropic laminate, taking into account any nonlinearity associated with either the applied load, the temperature, the humidity or any combinations among the three factors.

Since the classical laminated plate theory which is based on the macromechanical properties of the lamina predicts quite well the static properties of a composite laminate (9), it is assumed that the creep behavior of a laminated plate may also be describable by a suitable lamination theory if the macromechanical creep properties of the laminae are known, even though their individual responses may be nonlinear.

In the present paper, we chose to study the creep behavior of a glass-epoxy composite system. Uniaxial tensile creep tests were performed for a number of commonly used basic laminae, namely (0°), (90°) and ($\pm 45^\circ$)_S. Creep strains were measured against time for each of these basic laminae under various load, temperature and moisture conditions.

These results were then incorporated in a lamination theory to predict the creep response of a more practical laminate which contains the basic laminae. Namely, a so-called quasi-isotropic laminate is selected for verification of the theory. It will be shown that the theory predicted well the time-temperature-humidity-dependent creep behavior of the quasi-isotropic laminate.

II. EXPERIMENT

The basic material used in the experiment is the Sotctchply 1002 glass-epoxy unidirectional composite system, manufactured by the 3-M Company. Eight-ply laminates are made using unidirectional prepreg tape. The laminates are cured by the hot platen-press technique.

The test apparatus used in the static and creep experiments is Instron Universal tester, which is designed especially for dynamical loads. Temperature control is provided by an electrical oven, which can be affixed within the testing frame.

To maintain a constant moisture content in the specimens during the test is a very difficult task. In general, when exposed in dry air, the moisture content in the specimen will decrease due to desorption. On the other hand, if the specimen is kept wet during the test, an increase of moisture content will result. Thus, in either case, it is impossible to maintain a constant moisture content during the test. In the present experiment, we chose to wrap the specimen with a cotton cloth; hot water flows continuously but slowly over the wrapped specimen. This, however, will make the temperature in the specimen lower than the oven temperature due to vaporization. The actual temperature of the specimen is measured by a thermocouple attached to the specimen. On the other hand, the actual moisture content in the specimen is gradually increasing during the test. The increase, however, is considered insignificant, because the moisture absorption is a rather slow process.

Sensitivity and accuracy of the strain-measuring device during the creep tests is maintained by a calibrated extensometer. The precision of measurement of this device can reach 10^{-4} inch, which is satisfactory for the present study.

III. CREEP BEHAVIOR OF BASIC LAMINATES

The static uniaxial tensile test series are performed first to establish the basic-line information at room temperature. The results of these static tests are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Static Tensile Properties of
Glass-Epoxy Laminates At R.T.

<u>Lamination Type</u>	<u>Ultimate Tensile Strength psi x10³</u>	<u>Axial Modulus psi x 10⁶</u>
(90° _g)	2.0	1.38
(0° _g)	145	5.6
(±45°) _{2s}	20	1.41
(90/0/±45) _s	43	2.4

Creep tests are conducted in accordance with the static base-line information. Since creep deformation depends directly on the applied stress, the temperature, and the moisture content in the specimens, different shapes of creep curves are obtained for each combination of the three parameters. The fiber orientation in the lamina also controls the creep behavior of the laminate. The general effects of these parameters are discussed below for each of the three "basic laminates".

3.1 Creep Behavior of (90°) Laminate

In this configuration, the applied tensile load is normal to the fibers. Fig. 1 to 3 show the creep strain history of the (90°_g) specimens under various moisture contents at room temperature, 150°F and 215°F respectively. It is seen that at each given temperature, an increase in moisture content results in an increase of the creep strain rate. Also, at a given moisture content, the rate is larger at higher temperature. Thus, it is evident that the creep response is non-linear. Figure 1 shows, however, that a secondary creep is present. At low stress (1900 psi) low temperature (R.T.)/dry state, the creep response is nearly linear. Non-linear responses are found in all other cases.

From these results, the general belief is that the moisture-induced non-linearity is amplified by the effect of temperature and vice versa. In addition, early-time creep-rupture are also observed for some of the specimens when both the moisture and temperature levels are high.

The significance of the applied stress in the creep characteristics can be seen from the curves in Figure 4. When under high temperature and high moisture conditions, even a small variation in the applied stress will result in a large variation of creep deformation.

3.2. Creep Behavior Of (±45°)_{2s} Laminate

As for the (±45°)_{2s} laminates, large inplane shear deformation is observed; pronounced non-linear creep is resulted as the applied stress, the temperature and/or the moisture content increase. These results are displayed in Figures 6 to 8. As illustrated in Figure 7, for example, three specimens are tested under 150°F and 6700 psi (about 34% ultimate). Excessive non-linear creep is evident in the specimen with 1% moisture content.

Figure 5 shows a necking that occurred locally as a result of excessive in-plane shear deformation at elevated temperature. Similarly, Figure 8 shows a large initial strain and a large creep strain rate in the first stage of creep which is accompanied by a pronounced necking. These phenomena are clearly due to the softening of matrix near its glass transition temperature. When necking occurs in these specimens, creep-rupture is usually observed, Figure 8.

3.3 Creep Behavior Of (0°) Laminate

In the case of the (0°) specimens, the creep strain rate is controlled predominantly by the deformation of the fibers. Figure 9 shows the creep strain curves of a (0°) laminate in various environmental conditions. Here, moisture and/or temperature effects are less pronounced than observed in the (90°) or the (±45)_S laminates. At room temperature, in particular, creep deformation of the (0°) lamination is minimal. A definite increase in the creep strain is observed at high temperature and high moisture content conditions, Figure 9.

In summary, the creep response of the (90°) laminate is controlled predominantly by the matrix dilatation property while the creep response of the (±45)_S laminate is controlled by the matrix shear property, both of which behave non-linearly under either mechanical and/or hygrothermal loads. On the other hand, the creep response of the (0°) laminate is relatively insignificant; whether it is linear or non-linear does not bear any importance. However, in a laminate that consists of these elemental components in the laminations, such as the quasi-isotropic laminate, the non-linear creep response may not be ignored. But, the test results of the "basic laminate" may be used to predict the creep behavior of the quasi-isotropic laminate by means of a lamination theory. The development of this theory is discussed in the next section.

IV. A LAMINATION THEORY FOR CREEP DEFORMATION

4.1 Classical Lamination Theory For In-Plane Loading

In the classical laminated plate theory, the individual layers in the laminate are assumed to be macroscopically homogeneous but generally anisotropic (10). The plane stress-strain relation for each of the layers, say the kth layer, may be expressed as

$$\sigma_i^k = Q_{ij}^k \epsilon_j^k \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (1)$$

where Q_{ij}^k is the reduced planar stiffness matrix, which is related to the three-dimensional stiffness matrix C_{ij}^k of the kth layer, by

$$Q_{ij}^k = C_{ij}^k - \frac{C_{i3}^k C_{j3}^k}{C_{33}^k} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (2)$$

The in-plane resultant forces acting on the laminate are obtained by integrating the stresses in each layer through the laminated thickness,

$$N_i = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_i dz \quad (i = 1, 2, 6) \quad (3)$$

where h is total laminate thickness and z is the thickness-direction position coordinate, measured from the midplane of the laminate, Figure 10.

Figure 10:

Notation for Lamina Coordinates in a Laminate.

For symmetrical laminates, in-plane deformation is uncoupled with bending deformation (10); hence the constitutive equations for the laminate loaded by in-plane forces reduces to

$$N_i = A_{ij} \epsilon_j \quad (i, j=1, 2, 6) \quad (4)$$

where

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n (Q_{ij}^k) (z_k - z_{k-1}) \quad (5)$$

A_{ij} is known as the extensional stiffness matrix of the laminate.

4.2 Extension To In-Plane Viscoelastic Deformation

For a viscoelastic material, the time-dependent material property may be included in the laminate constitutive equations. By using Boltzmann Superposition principle, it can be written in the following incremental form

$$\Delta N_i = A_{ij}(t) \Delta \epsilon_j(t) \quad (i, j=1, 2, 6) \quad (6)$$

with time-dependent extensional stiffness expressed as

$$A_{ij}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n (z_k - z_{k-1}) Q_{ij}^k(t) \quad (7)$$

Following the lamination theory, the in-plane stiffness Q_{ij}^k of the k^{th} layer of a laminate may be calculated from the compliances S_{ij}^k . Actually, if the layers in the laminate are of the same unidirectional material, Q_{ij}^k for each layer can be calculated from the planar stiffness expressed in the principal material coordinates? Then

$$Q_{11}(t) = \frac{S_{22}(t)}{S_{11}(t) S_{22}(t) - S_{12}^2(t)}$$

$$Q_{22}(t) = \frac{S_{11}(t)}{S_{11}(t) S_{22}(t) - S_{12}^2(t)} \quad (8)$$

$$Q_{12}(t) = Q_{21}(t) = - \frac{S_{12}(t)}{S_{11}(t) S_{22}(t) - S_{12}^2(t)}$$

$$Q_{66}(t) = Q_{12}(t) = \frac{1}{S_{66}(t)}$$

$$Q_{16}(t) = Q_{26}(t) = 0$$

where the subscript 1 refers to the direction of fiber, 2 refers to the direction transverse to fiber and 6 refers to 1-2 plane. Here $S_{11}(t)$, $S_{22}(t)$ and $S_{66}(t)$ are the creep compliances of the basic orthotropic layer comprising the laminate. Based on a linear viscoelastic assumption, $S_{11}(t)$, $S_{22}(t)$ can be obtained from the uniaxial loaded creep test results of (0°) and (90°) laminates by means of a quasi-elastic approximation (11):

$$S_{11}(t) = \frac{e_1(t)}{\sigma_1} \quad (9)$$

$$S_{22}(t) = \frac{e_2(t)}{\sigma_2}$$

where σ and $e(t)$ are the applied stresses and the resulting creep strain respectively. On the other hand, the shear compliance $S_{66}(t)$ can be obtained from the creep test results of $(45^\circ)_{2S}$ laminates under uniaxial loading. Following Rosen's approach (12), we have

$$S_{66}(t) = \frac{e_{12}(t)}{\sigma_{12}} = \frac{2[e_x(t) - e_y(t)]}{\sigma_x} \quad (10)$$

where the uniaxial tension stress of x-direction

$$\sigma_x = 2\sigma_{12}$$

The shear strain $e_{12}(t) = e_x(t) - e_y(t)$

Let us return to Eqn. (6). Eqn. (6) is the basic equation for calculating the viscoelastic deformation of a symmetric laminate subjected to in-plane loading, regardless whether the laminate behaves linearly or non-linearly. However, when specialized to constant uniaxial load N_x acting in x direction (see Figure 10), Eqn. (6) can be simplified as:

$$N_x = A_{ij} (\sigma^k, t_n) \epsilon_x (t_n) \quad (11)$$

where t_n is any given time $0 < t_n < \infty$ and ϵ_x the creep strain of the laminate in the load direction. A_{ij} depend, in general, on the stress levels in each of the laminae of the laminate.

Since at a given time t_n the strain field in each lamina of the laminate is the same in planar deformation, we have

$$\epsilon_x(t_n) = \epsilon_x^k(t_n) = \epsilon_x^0(t_n) = \epsilon_x^{+45}(t_n) \quad (12)$$

From Eqn. (9), the extensional stiffness A_{ij} of a quasi-isotropic composite laminate under a given load may be expressed, after proper coordinate transformations of each layer based on Eqn. (8);

$$A_{ij}(t_n) = \frac{h}{8} [2Q_{ij}^0(t_n) + 2Q_{ij}^{90}(t_n) + 4Q_{ij}^{+45}(t_n)] \quad (13)$$

thus,

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11}(t_n) &= A_{22}(t_n) = \frac{h}{8} \{3[Q_{11}(t_n) + Q_{22}(t_n)] \\ &\quad + 2[Q_{12}(t_n) + 2Q_{66}(t_n)]\} \\ A_{12}(t_n) &= \frac{h}{8} [6Q_{12}(t_n) + Q_{11}(t_n) + Q_{22}(t_n) \\ &\quad - 4Q_{66}(t_n)] \\ A_{66}(t_n) &= \frac{h}{8} [4Q_{66}(t_n) + Q_{11}(t_n) + Q_{22}(t_n) \\ &\quad - 2Q_{12}(t_n)] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$A_{16}(t_n) = A_{26}(t_n) = 0$$

From Eqns. (8), (9) and (10), it is seen that $A_{ij}(t_n)$ may also be expressed by the creep compliance $S_{ij}(t)$ of the "basic laminae." However, since all S_{ij} depend on the stress level that exists in each layer at time t , Eqn. (14) cannot be evaluated without knowing the stresses in the layers at time t_n . To overcome this difficulty, the following procedures are followed:

From the known uniaxial tensile creep curves (see section III) for the $(0^\circ)_g$,

(90°_g) or (±45°)_{2S} specimens at stress level, say σ_0^k , the creep strain in the load direction at time t_n and under a different stress $\sigma_1^k(t_n)$ may be approximated by a power relation

$$\frac{e^k(t_n, \sigma_1^k)}{e^k(t_n, \sigma_0^k)} = \left(\frac{\sigma_1^k}{\sigma_0^k}\right)^n$$

or

$$e_x^k(t_n, \sigma_1^k) = e_x^k(t_n, \sigma_0^k) \left(\frac{\sigma_1^k}{\sigma_0^k}\right)^n \tag{15}$$

where n is a constant, and a function of the fiber orientation and temperature. The constant n may be obtained from experimental data. Where $e_1^k(t_n, \sigma_0^k)$ is the creep strain of k^{th} ply at t_n and σ_0^k , and $e_1^k(t_n, \sigma_1^k)$ is the creep strain of k^{th} ply at t_n and σ_1^k .

Defining,

$$\Delta e_x^k(t_n, \sigma_1^k) = e_x^k(t_n, \sigma_1^k) - e_x^k(t_{n-1}, \sigma_1^k) \tag{16}$$

we have (11)

$$S_{11}^k(t_n) = \frac{\epsilon_x(t_{n-1}) + \Delta e_x^k(t_n, \sigma_1^k)}{\sigma_1^k(t_n)} \tag{17}$$

where $\epsilon_x(t_{n-1})$ is defined in Eqn. (12).

Since average compliance $\bar{S}_{ij}(t_n)$ during the time increment $t_n = (t_n - t_{n-1})$ is approximated by

$$\bar{S}_{ij}(t_n) = \frac{S_{ij}(t_n) + S_{ij}(t_{n-1})}{2} \tag{18}$$

Having defined S_{ij} at t_n and σ_1^k , we can return to Eqn. (14) and define the planar stiffness accordingly. In this manner, the non-linear nature of the creep responses of the laminae is included in defining Eqn. (14).

Following the same steps, we can compute the creep strain at $t = t_{n+1}$; $t = t_{n+2}$, $t = t_{n+3}$; etc.. A continuous creep strain curve for the laminate under a constant load and same environmental condition is then constructed. Figure 11.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the experiments and analysis described in this paper, the following conclusions may be made:

1. The creep behavior of (90°) glass-epoxy laminates is strongly affected by temperature and moisture. The degradation of this material is found to be quite serious when the temperature and moisture content increase. The specimen may fail by creep-rupture within a few hours after loading at high temperature/high moisture conditions, even at low stress levels.

2. Temperature and moisture also have significant effect on $(\pm 45)_2$ s glass-epoxy laminates. When the temperature level is high, a large in-plane shear deformation is accompanied by necking, and change of orientation of fibers can be clearly observed. Debonding and delamination of the laminate usually proceed a creep-rupture.

3. Fiber orientation of the laminate is a major factor in determining the creep behavior of the laminate. Creep strain is insignificant in the (0°) laminate especially at low temperature and low moisture conditions. However, a definite increase in creep strain is observed in the (0°) specimens at high temperature and high moisture content conditions.

4. An analytical prediction of non-linear uniaxial creep of a more general laminate can be devised if we know the creep behavior of the laminae which the laminate contains. The example problems worked out in this paper indicate a reasonable agreement with the experiment results. Obviously, the comparison is based only on a few simple cases. The analytical method should be examined more generally by other practical cases, such as biaxial, torsion and bending creep tests, to mention a few.

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Figure 1: Creep of (90°) Laminate At RT And Various Moisture Contents (1900 psi)

Figure 2: Creep of (90°) Laminate At 150°F And Various Moisture Contents (900 psi)

Figure 3: Creep of (90°) Laminate At 215°F And Various Moisture Contents (900 psi)

Figure 4: The Effect of Stress Level On Creep Strain For (90°) Laminates At 215°F And $0.5\% \text{ MC}$

Figure 5: The $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2S}$ Specimens After Creep TEST

Figure 6: Creep of $(\pm 45)_{2S}$ Laminates At RT And Various Moisture Contents (6700 psi)

Figure 7: Creep of $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2s}$ Laminates At 150°F And Various Moisture Contents (6700 psi)

Figure 8: Creep of $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2s}$ Laminate At 215°F And Various Moisture Contents (6700 psi)

Figure 9: Creep of (0°) Laminate Under Various Environmental Condition (46600 psi)

Figure 11: Comparison of Theoretical And Experimental Creep for Quasi-Isotropic Laminate (14000 psi)